

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Nickens**FIRST NAME:** Michelle**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Cleenewerck

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: Word 365

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What does an academic essay aim to accomplish?

- Explain your view on an issue to a group of experts in that field of study.
- Persuade readers on an idea based on evidence.¹**
- Prove other research does not use evidence to prove a thesis.
- Experiment with creative and complex ideas.

2. Based on the original quotation below, which selection would not be considered plagiarism?

From the 1950s to the 2000s, law enforcement agencies addressed crime and its evolution with improved strategies and began to share critical information with each other. However, it was the events of 9/11 that served as a catalyst for state, local, tribal, territorial, and federal law enforcement and homeland security agencies to improve their ability to develop and share criminal intelligence and information.

¹EUCLID University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>.

- The tragedies of September 11, 2001 were the impetus for law enforcement and homeland security entities to create information and intelligence sharing capabilities.
- For decades prior to 2000, “law enforcement agencies addressed crime and its evolution with improved strategies and began to share critical information with each other.”
- The events of 9/11 resulted in criminal justice leaders working together to help break down the information sharing silos that have existed for decades (Bureau of Justice Assistance 2013, 4).²**
- September 11, 2001 serves as a catalyst for changing how criminal intelligence and information is shared.

3. **Which of the following is not a goal of a research project?**

- Using the Internet as a source of information.³**
- Finding an answer that you can support with good reasons.
- Identifying reliable evidence to support your argument.
- Drafting a report that makes a good case for your answer.

² Bureau of Justice Assistance, “National Criminal Intelligence Sharing Plan Version 2.0,” 2013, 4. <https://it.ojp.gov/GIST/150/File/National%20Criminal%20Intelligence%20Sharing%20Plan%20version%2002.pdf>.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 26 & 29.

4. **What tool helps researchers discover keywords, identify common trends, and refine the flow of a research paper?**

- Storyboarding⁴**
- i2 Analyst's Notebook
- Microsoft Excel
- Zotero

5. **Which of the below is an example of a primary source?**

- Original costumes by a production designer.⁵**
- A biography of a famous costumer.
- An encyclopedia entry about costume design.
- None of the above.

6. **How does a researcher earn a reader's trust?**

- Ensuring a detailed, open, and honest approach.
- Providing proven and reliable sources and thoroughly documenting citations.
- Acknowledging and responding to other points of view and disagreements.
- All of the above.⁶**

⁴ Turabian, 22–23.

⁵ Turabian, 24–26.

⁶ Turabian, 25, 38, 86.

7. **What are the attributes of qualitative research?**

- Collects information or makes observations to test a hypothesis or theory.
- Provides a black and white approach to ensure researchers stay focused.
- Integrates an open-ended and exploratory approach to understanding a phenomenon.**⁷
- Includes facts and objective statements as evidence.

8. **Select the best Purpose Statement from those provided below.**

- Since the beginning of time, art has been a method to document history. In this paper, the theories provided will create a foundation to build a strong base of knowledge of how art impacts and illustrates conflict.
- As people flee their homeland, the reasons behind the exodus remain a mystery. This dissertation will provide strategies to solve the conflict in South America.
- Information sharing among law enforcement is a critical component to solving crimes and safeguarding communities. This research paper will identify the most effective and meaningful information sharing strategies that meet the diverse needs of local and state law enforcement agencies and that are replicable in other jurisdictions.**⁸
- Everyone wants cost-effective and efficient health care. This paper will show how to re-engineer the health care system, how to deliver health care to all citizens, how to save money and tax dollars, and how to ensure payment to health care professionals.

⁷ Adu, Philip. 2016. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* by Philip Adu, Ph.D. MP4. Chicago: National Center for Academic & Dissertation Excellence. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&t=407s>.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008), 35–37.

9. **What purpose does a literature review serve?**

- To provide a clear and balanced picture of current concepts, theories, and data.⁹**
- To create a balanced flow of information for a research paper.
- To give other researchers credit for their information.
- To find gaps in other researcher's data and theories.

10. **Which qualitative data collection method focuses on interaction and dialogue among participants and enables diverse and meaningful responses?**

- Interviews
- Focus Group¹⁰**
- Observation
- Survey

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⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 46.

¹⁰ Ibid., 195.

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